

Radio Frequency Subsystems and Satellite Communication

Presented by

Olarewaju Peter Ayeoribe

ayeoribe.olarewaju@fuoye.edu.ng

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering
Federal University Oye-Ekiti

January 2023

Radio Frequency Subsystems and Satellite
Communication by Olarewaju Peter
Ayeoribe. Department of Electrical and
Electronic Engineering Federal University
Oye-Ekiti

Unit I

- **Satellite Communications: Overview of regulations and elements that make up Satellite; Communications Systems; Communications link and the factors that affect system performance**

Aim & Objectives

- To understand the basics of satellite overview of regulations.
- To acquire the knowledge about elements that makes up Satellite.

Overview

- Satellite is a microwave repeater in the space.
- There are about 750 satellite in the space, most of them are used for communication.
- They are:
 - Wide area coverage of the earth's surface.
 - Transmission delay is about 0.3 sec.
 - Transmission cost is independent of distance.

Overview of the law and regulation

- Among the numerous applications of satellite systems, a large and growing one is the provision of Internet services. Technological advances mean that satellites can provide broadband communications to large areas (including entire regions or even continents) at minimal extra marginal cost. Satellites also support communication services in remote and rural areas and are generally resilient to terrestrial natural disasters, such as earthquakes or tsunamis. Satellite systems can provide continuous and consistent service with very wide geographic coverage, including to ships and aircraft.

•Satellites are shrinking in size, their typical data rates are increasing, enabling satellite systems to offer and transmit increasingly advanced services across more locations help explain the rising uptake of satellite-based communication systems. However, geostationary orbital (GSO) slots, as well as space in general, are becoming increasingly crowded. With GSO demand still heating up, radio-interference between services becomes a growing risk, while concerns also arise over space debris.

-
- Satellites are specifically made for telecommunication purpose. They are used for mobile applications such as communication to ships, vehicles, planes, hand-held terminals and for TV and radio broadcasting
 - Satellite coverage spans great distances
 - A satellite can directly connect points separated by 1000's of miles
 - A satellite can broadcast to 1000's of homes/businesses/military installations simultaneously
 - A satellite can be reached from ground facilities that move
 - Satellites can connect to locations with no infrastructure
 - Satellites adapt easily to changing requirements

Overview of the law and regulation of satellite services

- ITU oversees the allocation of the radio frequencies required to meet the continuously evolving needs of the satellite industry.
- ITU also manages a cooperative satellite frequency registration process.

Overview of regulation

- Most of the fixed satellite service frequency bands are shared with the terrestrial systems. For them to coexist, the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) has specified certain constraints in the transmitted effective radiated power (EIRP) of satellites.

Overview of regulation

- ITU manages a cooperative system of international coordination
- on the radio frequencies used by satellites, aimed at preventing such systems from interfering
- ITU also manages a cooperative satellite frequency registration process.

International Regulations

- The Federal Communications Commission regulates interstate and international communications by radio, television, wire, satellite and cable in all 50 states, the District of Columbia and U.S. territories.

Overview of regulation

- The ITU Radio Regulations and ITU Constitution (No. 197 of Article 45) provide that “all stations, whatever their purpose, must be established and operated in such a manner as not to cause harmful interference to the radio services or communications of other Members, recognized operating agencies, or other authorized operating agencies which carry on a radio service, and which operate in accordance with the Radio Regulations”.

Satellite Communications

Terminology

- **Ground station** (also “ground terminal”)
 - sends signals to/receives signals from a satellite
- **Modulator, demodulator** (modulator + demodulator = modem)
 - Ground station component: **modulator** converts digital “1”s and “0”s to a radio frequency signal (**modulated carrier**) that can be transmitted
 - Demodulator recovers digital “1”s and “0”s from the modulated carrier
- **Carrier frequency**
 - The center frequency of a modulated carrier
- **Frequency band**
 - The frequency range containing the carrier frequency
 - Satellite communications frequency bands are standardized
 - Within the US, the FCC defines frequency bands for satcom; coordinates specific frequency assignments;
 - Outside the US, the International Telecommunications Union has the same role
- **Frequency conversion** (up-conversion, down-conversion)
 - The process by which the carrier frequency is changed to accommodate standards or hardware limitations
- **Up-link** – the link from the ground terminal to the satellite
- **Down-link** – the link from the satellite to the ground terminal

Satellite Communications Process

- Digital information from user arrives at a “**ground station**”.
- Digital signal goes into a *modulator*, converting digital information into a
- **modulated carrier**.
- **Carrier frequency** is changed (**up-converted**) to place it in the desired frequency range (**up-link frequency band**) for transmission to the satellite
- Carrier is amplified
- The ground station **antenna** radiates the carrier toward the satellite
- The signal passes through earth’s atmosphere (~10 miles thick) and continues on to satellite ~22,300 miles away
- The satellite receives signal and changes (**down-converts**) the carrier frequency to the **down-link frequency band**.
- The satellite amplifies the carrier
- Amplified carrier is re-radiated toward earth through the satellite antenna.
- Received carrier is picked up by earth station antenna, amplified, and changed to a frequency that the **demodulator** can process.
- Demodulator recovers original digital information from carrier, though not perfectly; errors are always present!

Elements that make up Satellite, communications Systems

The main components of a satellite consist of the communications system, which includes the antennas and transponders that receive and retransmit signals, the power system, which includes the solar panels that provide power, and the propulsion system, which includes the rockets that propel the satellite

Components that make up Satellite, communications Systems

- Satellite communication has two main components: **the ground segment, which consists of fixed or mobile transmission, reception, and ancillary equipment, and the space segment, which primarily is the satellite itself**

Elements that make up Satellite, communications Systems

- Components of a satellite also consist of the communications system, which includes the antennas and transponders that receive and retransmit signals, the power system, which includes the solar panels that provide power, and the propulsion system, which includes the rockets that propel the satellite

Types of Satellite communication services

- There are three types of communication services that satellites provide: **telecommunications, broadcasting, and data communications.** Telecommunication services include telephone calls and services provided to telephone companies, as well as wireless, mobile, and cellular network providers

Factors that affect Satellite Communication performance

- Costs are Prohibitive. Satellites are expensive.
- Signal Reception can be Spotty. Another problem with satellites is their somewhat unreliable signal.
- Propagation Delay is a Problem. ...
- There are No Repair Shops in Space.
- Congestion of frequencies. This can cause a disruption of the communication services.
- Interference and proliferation.

Unit 2

- Satellite orbits, the location of a satellite from the earth, and satellite control; Examples of different kinds of satellite are given, together with the functions of subsystems, such as power generation, attitude control, transponders and antennas

Objectives

- ❖ To understand the basics of satellite orbits.
- ❖ To analyze the geo stationary and non geo stationary orbits.
- ❖ To acquire the knowledge about launching procedures.

Satellites orbits

- Satellites orbit around the earth. Depending on the application, these orbits can be circular or elliptical. Satellites in circular orbits always keep the same distance to the earth's surface following a simple law:

The attractive force F_g of the earth due to gravity equals

$$m \cdot g \left(\frac{R}{r} \right)^2$$

The centrifugal force F_c trying to pull the satellite away equals

- $m \cdot r \cdot \omega^2$

Satellites orbits

▪ **The path followed by a satellite is referred to as its orbit.** Satellite orbits are matched to the capability and objective of the sensor(s) they carry. Orbit selection can vary in terms of altitude (their height above the Earth's surface) and their orientation and rotation relative to the Earth

Types of Satellites orbits

▪ An orbit is a regular, repeating path that an object in space takes around another one. An object moving around a planet in an orbit is called a satellite. According to the height of satellites from the earth, the orbits can be classified as **High Earth orbit, Medium Earth orbit, and Low Earth orbit**

Satellites Contd

- Satellites antenna patterns play an important role and must be designed to best cover the designated geographical area (which is generally irregular in shape).
- Satellites should be designed by keeping in mind its usability for short and long term effects throughout its life time.
- The earth station should be in a position to control the satellite if it drifts from its orbit it is subjected to any kind of drag from the external forces

Orbital parameters

- **Apogee:** A point for a satellite farthest from the Earth. It is denoted as **ha**.
- **Perigee:** A point for a satellite closest from the Earth. It is denoted as **hp**.
- **Line of Apsides:** Line joining perigee and apogee through centre of the Earth. It is the major axis of the orbit. One-half of this line's length is the semi-major axis equivalent to satellite's mean distance from the Earth.
- **Ascending Node:** The point where the orbit crosses the equatorial plane going from north to south.
- **Descending Node:** The point where the orbit crosses the equatorial plane going from south to north.

Orbital parameters

- **Descending Node:** The point where the orbit crosses the equatorial plane going from south to north.
- **Inclination:** the angle between the orbital plane and the Earth's equatorial plane. Its measured at the ascending node from the equator to the orbit, going from East to North. Also, this angle is commonly denoted as i .
- **Line of Nodes:** the line joining the ascending and descending nodes through the centre of Earth.
- **Prograde Orbit:** an orbit in which satellite moves in the same direction as the Earth's rotation. Its inclination is always between 00 to 900. Many satellites follow this path as Earth's velocity makes it easier to lunch these satellites.
- **Retrograde Orbit:** an orbit in which satellite moves in the same direction counter to the Earth's rotation.

Orbital parameters

- **Argument of Perigee:** An angle from the point of perigee measure in the orbital plane at the Earth's centre, in the direction of the satellite motion.
- **Right ascension of ascending node:** The definition of an orbit in space, the position of ascending node is specified. But as the Earth spins, the longitude of ascending node changes and cannot be used for reference. Thus for practical determination of an orbit, the longitude and time of crossing the ascending node is used for absolute measurement, a fixed reference point in space is required.
- **Mean anomaly:** It gives the average value to the angular position of the satellite with reference to the perigee.

Common Satellite Orbits

- LEO (Low Earth Orbit)
 - Close to Earth
 - Photo satellites – 250 miles
 - Iridium – 490 miles
- Polar Orbit
 - Provides coverage to polar regions (used by Russian satellites)
- GEO (Geosynchronous Earth Orbit)
 - Angular velocity of the satellite = angular velocity of earth
- satellite appears to be fixed in space
 - Most widely used since ground antennas need not move
 - Circular orbit
 - Altitude: 22,236 miles
 - Can't "see" the poles

Orbits

- **LEO:** Low Earth Orbit.
- **MEO:** Medium Earth Orbit
- **GEO:** Geostationary Earth Orbit

Geostationary orbit

- At the Geostationary orbit the satellite covers 42.2% of the earth's surface.
- Theoretically 3 geostationary satellites provides 100% earth coverage

Geostationary orbit Contd

- Most SATCOMs are in Geosynchronous Orbit
 - Most of these are in GEO Stationary orbits.
- Some SATCOM systems reside in Low Earth Orbit (LEO)
 - For example IRIDIUM.
 - Useful for global coverage including the polar regions.

Orbital Planes

- The GPS Constellation utilises the Medium Earth Orbit

Satellite Communications Terminology

- **Ground station** (also “ground terminal”)
 - sends signals to/receives signals from a satellite
- **Modulator, demodulator** (modulator + demodulator = modem)
 - Ground station component: **modulator** converts digital “1”s and “0”s to a radio frequency signal (**modulated carrier**) that can be transmitted
 - Demodulator recovers digital “1”s and “0”s from the modulated carrier
- **Carrier frequency**
 - The center frequency of a modulated carrier
- **Frequency band**
 - The frequency range containing the carrier frequency
 - Satellite communications frequency bands are standardized
 - Within the US, the FCC defines frequency bands for satcom; coordinates specific frequency assignments;
 - Outside the US, the International Telecommunications Union has the same role
- **Frequency conversion** (up-conversion, down-conversion)
 - The process by which the carrier frequency is changed to accommodate standards or hardware limitations
- **Up-link** – the link from the ground terminal to the satellite
- **Down-link** – the link from the satellite to the ground terminal

Satellite Communications Process

- Digital information from user arrives at a “**ground station**”.
- Digital signal goes into a *modulator*, converting digital information into a
- **modulated carrier**.
- **Carrier frequency** is changed (**up-converted**) to place it in the desired frequency range (**up-link frequency band**) for transmission to the satellite
- Carrier is amplified
- The ground station **antenna** radiates the carrier toward the satellite
- The signal passes through earth’s atmosphere (~10 miles thick) and continues on to satellite ~22,300 miles away
- The satellite receives signal and changes (**down-converts**) the carrier frequency to the **down-link frequency band**.
- The satellite amplifies the carrier
- Amplified carrier is re-radiated toward earth through the satellite antenna.
- Received carrier is picked up by earth station antenna, amplified, and changed to a frequency that the **demodulator** can process.
- Demodulator recovers original digital information from carrier, though not perfectly; errors are always present!

Antenna Key Points

- One antenna talks to only one satellite!
- Antenna-satellite association must be unique to avoid interference
 - Small antennas have advantage of compactness, but
 - Communications design for ground terminals with small antennas requires care to avoid interference

- **Unit III : Earth Stations , their Antenna Configuration and Tracking Requirement**

Objectives

- To understand the satellite segment and earth segment.
- To analyze the Satellite Uplink and Downlink.
- To understand the G/T ratio-Performance Impairments-System noise.

Spacecraft Technology- Structure

- A satellite communications system can be broadly divided into two segments—a ground segment and a space segment.
- The space segment will obviously include the satellites, but it also includes the ground facilities needed to keep the satellites operational, these being referred to as the *tracking, telemetry, and command* (TT&C) facilities. In many networks it is common practice to employ a ground station solely for the purpose of TT&C

- The equipment carried aboard the satellite also can be classified according to function. The *payload* refers to the equipment used to provide the service for which the satellite has been launched. In a communications satellite, the equipment which provides the connecting link between the satellite's transmit and receive antennas is referred to as the *transponder*. The transponder forms one of the main sections of the payload, the other being the antenna subsystems. In this chapter the main characteristics of certain bus systems and payloads are described.

The Power Supply

- The primary electrical power for operating the electronic equipment is obtained from solar cells. Individual cells can generate only small amounts of power, and therefore, arrays of cells in series-parallel connection are required.
- During eclipse, power is provided by two nickel-cadmium (Ni-Cd) long-life batteries, which will deliver 830 W. At the end of life, battery recharge time is less than 16 h.

Attitude Control & Orbit Control

- The *attitude* of a satellite refers to its orientation in space. Much of the equipment carried aboard a satellite is there for the purpose of controlling its attitude. Attitude control is necessary, for example, to ensure that directional antennas point in the proper directions.
- In the case of earth environmental satellites, the earth-sensing instruments must cover the required regions of the earth, which also requires attitude control. A number of forces, referred to as *disturbance torques*, can alter the attitude, some examples being the gravitational fields of the earth and the moon, solar radiation, and meteorite impacts.

- Attitude control must not be confused with station keeping, which is the term used for maintaining a satellite in its correct orbital position, although the two are closely related.

To exercise attitude control, there must be available some measure of a satellite's orientation in space and of any tendency for this to shift. In one method, infrared sensors, referred to as *horizon detectors*, are used to detect the rim of the earth against the background of space.

With the use of four such sensors, one for each quadrant, the center of the earth can be readily established as a reference point.

Usually, the attitude-control process takes place aboard the satellite, but it is also possible for control signals to be transmitted from earth, based on attitude data obtained from the satellite.

Also, where a shift in attitude is desired, an *attitude maneuver* is executed. The control signals needed to achieve this maneuver may be transmitted from an earth station.

▪ Controlling torques may be generated in a number of ways. *Passive attitude control* refers to the use of mechanisms which stabilize the satellite without putting a drain on the satellite's energy supplies; at most, infrequent use is made of these supplies, for example, when thruster jets are impulse to provide corrective torque. Examples of passive attitude control are *spin stabilization* and *gravity gradient stabilization*.

▪ The other form of attitude control is *active control*. With active attitude control, there is no overall stabilizing torque present to resist the disturbance torques. Instead, corrective torques are applied as required in response to disturbance torques. Methods used to generate active control torques include momentum wheels, electromagnetic coils, and mass expulsion devices, such as gas jets and ion thrusters.

A transponder is capable of :

- Receiving uplinked radio signals from earth satellite transmission stations (antennas).
- Amplifying received radio signals
- Sorting the input signals and directing the output signals through input/output signal multiplexers to the proper downlink antennas for retransmission to earth satellite receiving stations (antennas).

- Data which are transmitted as telemetry signals include attitude information such as that obtained from sun and earth sensors; environmental information such as the magnetic field intensity and direction, the frequency of meteorite impact, and so on; and spacecraft information such as temperatures, power supply voltages, and stored-fuel pressure.

Encryption

- Thus attitude changes may be made, communication transponders switched in and out of circuits, antennas redirected, and station-keeping maneuvers carried out on command. It is clearly important to prevent unauthorized commands from being received and decoded, and for this reason, the command signals are often encrypted.
- *Encrypt* is derived from a Greek word *kryptein*, meaning *to hide*, and represents the process of concealing the command signals in a secure code. This differs from the normal process of encoding which converts characters in the command signal into a code suitable for transmission.

Transponders

- A transponder is the series of interconnected units which forms a single communications channel between the receive and transmit antennas in a communications satellite.
- Some of the units utilized by a transponder in a given channel may be common to a number of transponders. Thus, although reference may be made to a specific transponder, this must be thought of as an equipment *channel* rather than a single item of equipment.
- Before describing in detail the various units of a transponder, the overall frequency arrangement of a typical C-band communications satellite will be examined briefly. The bandwidth allocated for C-band service is 500 MHz, and this is divided into subbands, one transponder.

The Power Amplifier

- The fixed attenuation is needed to balance out variations in the input attenuation so that each transponder channel has the same nominal attenuation, the necessary adjustments being made during assembly.
- The variable attenuation is needed to set the level as required for different types of service (an example being the requirement for input power backoff discussed later). Because this variable attenuator adjustment is an operational requirement, it must be under the control of the ground TT&C station.
- *Traveling-wave tube amplifiers (TWTAs)* are widely used in transponders to provide the final output power required to the transmit antenna.

TRAVELING WAVE TUBE (TWT)

In the TWT, an electron-beam gun assembly consisting of a heater, a cathode, and focusing electrodes is used to form an electron beam. A magnetic field is required to confine the beam to travel along the inside of a wire helix.

Advantage Of The TWT Over Other Types Of Tube Amplifiers

- The advantage of the TWT over other types of tube amplifiers is that it can provide amplification over a very wide bandwidth. Input levels to the TWT must be carefully controlled, however, to minimize the effects of certain forms of distortion.

INTER MODULATION AND INTERFERENCE

- Intermodulation interference is the undesired combining of several signals in a nonlinear device, producing new, unwanted frequencies, which can cause interference in adjacent receivers located at repeater sites.
- Not all interference is a result of intermodulation distortion. It can come from co-channel interference, atmospheric conditions as well as man-made noise generated by medical, welding and heating equipment.
- Most intermodulation occurs in a transmitter's nonlinear power amplifier (PA). The next most common mixing point is in the front end of a receiver. Usually it occurs in the unprotected first mixer of older model radios or in some cases an overdriven RF front-end amp.
- Intermodulation can also be produced in rusty or corroded tower joints, guy wires, turnbuckles and anchor rods or any nearby metallic object, which can act as a nonlinear "mixer/rectifier" device.

Propagation Characteristics and Frequency considerations

- A number of factors resulting from changes in the atmosphere have to be taken into account when designing a satellite communications system in order to avoid impairment of the wanted signal.
- Generally, a margin in the required carrier-to-noise ratio is incorporated to accommodate such effects.

Radio Noise

- Radio noise emitted by matter is used as a source of information in radio astronomy and in remote sensing. Noise of a thermal origin has a continuous spectrum, but several other radiation mechanisms cause the emission to have a spectral-line structure. Atoms and molecules are distinguished by their different spectral lines.
- For other services such as satellite communications noise is a limiting factor for the receiving system; generally, it is inappropriate to use receiving systems with noise temperatures which are much less than those specified by the minimum external noise.
- From about 30 MHz to about 1 GHz cosmic noise predominates over atmospheric noise except during local thunderstorms, but will generally be exceeded by man-made noise in populated areas.
- In the bands of strong gaseous absorption, the noise temperature reaches maximum values of some 290 K. At times, precipitation will also increase the noise temperature at frequencies above 5 GHz

10-Questions and Answers on Radio Frequency Subsystems and Satellite Communication

- List the eight components of an electromagnetic Spectrum and their benefit to man

Solution:

- The entire electromagnetic spectrum, from the lowest to the highest frequency (longest to shortest wavelength), includes all **radio waves (e.g., commercial radio and television, microwaves, radar), infrared radiation, visible light, ultraviolet radiation, X-rays, and gamma rays.**

What are the benefits of electromagnetic waves?

- EM interactions can provide spatiotemporal information on the near-Earth space environment (geospace).
- These include **nerve regeneration, wound healing, graft behavior, diabetes, and myocardial and cerebral ischemia (heart attack and stroke)**, among other conditions. Preliminary data even suggest possible benefits in controlling malignancy.

What are the harmful effects of electromagnetic waves to humans?

- Reported symptoms include **headaches, anxiety, suicide and depression, nausea, fatigue and loss of libido**

What are the three basic components of all electromagnetic signals?

- **Frequency, wavelength and speed** are three key parameters for any electromagnetic wave.

What are the 4 main properties of electromagnetic waves explain each?

- The following are the primary qualities of electromagnetic waves: Transverse electromagnetic waves exist in nature, and electric and magnetic fields are proportional to each other. The oscillations of and are perpendicular to each other and are in the same phase. Electromagnetic waves do not require a medium to travel.

Explain the terms centrifugal and centripetal in satellite communication system.

- **Centripetal acceleration** is the radial acceleration of an object in circular motion.
- The net radial force acting on an object that keeps it moving in a circle is the **centripetal force**. The centripetal force vector points in the same direction as the acceleration vector according to Newton's second law.

What is the Difference between centripetal and centrifugal forces in Geography

- Centrifugal forces divide a state and can lead to a disruption of internal order or balkanization. Centripetal forces unify a state by providing stability and creating solidarity.

Discuss the three important reason for simulating RF and microwave circuits and system

- This application note describes **system-level** characterization and **modeling** techniques for **radio frequency (RF)** and **microwave** subsystem components.
- The primary application of RF and Microwaves in today's world is in **wireless technologies**. Technologies like – wireless communications, wireless networking, wireless security systems, radar systems, medical engineering, and remote sensing.

List four disadvantages of digital transmission of communication signals.

- **Disadvantages of Digital Communication**
- There is high power consumption in digital communication.
- There is a requirement for synchronization in the case of synchronous modulation.
- There is a sampling error.
- The most common limitation of digital communication is that it requires more transmission bandwidth.

What Maxwell's equation explain?

- Maxwell's equations are **a set of four equations that describe the behavior of electric and magnetic fields and how they relate to each other.** Ultimately they demonstrate that electric and magnetic fields are two manifestations of the same phenomenon. where c is recognized as the speed of light.